

Buckling of Continuous Filament Composite Isogrid Panels: Theory and Experiment

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ABSTRACT

The first stylus woven composite stiffened structure to undergo extensive structural evaluation is isogrid. A significant finding of the experimental research is that transverse shear deformation and related effects are important for this type of construction. A new theory for bending-related behavior of flat isogrid plates which consistently accounts for these effects is presented. This paper deals with the development of the theory and its application to compressive buckling problems. Buckling load predictions for wide columns are in good agreement with experimental data. This adds important evidence in support of the new theory.

INTRODUCTION

The search for efficient, light-weight aerospace structural concepts is a continuing process. One proven concept used in boosters and spacecraft is isogrid. It is a stiffening concept that employs a repetitive equilateral triangular pattern of ribs as shown in Figure 1. The name "isogrid" refers to the fact that the triangular grid exhibits isotropic properties in a gross sense.

New tooling concepts and fiber placement methods permit the traditional advantages of stiffening to be further enhanced by the benefits attributable to modern composite material systems. A unique, promising method for manufacturing stiffened composite structures called stylus weaving (1) has been employed by the McDonnell Douglas Astronautics Company - St. Louis to produce an isogrid structure. The ribs of the grid are constructed of continuous unidirectional fibers. The process is economical because it is automated. The manufacturing details are presented in Reference 2. All of the evaluation to date of this type of structure has been performed at the Georgia Institute of Technology (2 - 6). The existing technology base is summarized in Reference 4.

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A significant finding that emerged from this research is that transverse shear deformation effects are significant for this type of construction. The weaving process renders the stiffeners or ribs very nearly unidirectional with the fibers aligned with the rib axis. While this is enormously efficient structurally as the stiffeners carry predominantly uniaxial bending stresses, the transverse shear stiffness that results is relatively low and is largely controlled by the resin matrix properties. This is responsible for the observed bending and buckling dependence on transverse shear characteristics. This finding is documented in References 2-6.

Recent theoretical research (7) has contributed a new appreciation for other nonclassical factors in addition to transverse shear deformation in bending-related behavior. A nonclassical contribution to axial stress and transverse normal strain affect response in planar bending situations significantly for certain combinations of geometry and stiffness. The fundamental ideas of this work are the cornerstone of a new theory for bending and buckling of plates (8), stiffened plates (9) and the work presented here.

The theory for continuous filament isogrid plates is physically similar to that of orthogonally stiffened plates given in Reference 9. The differences are solely due to the geometric pattern of the isogrid stiffening. For this reason, only pertinent results are cited herein. Reference 9 provides the detailed theoretical foundation. Representative examples are provided to illustrate the significance of nonclassical influences on behavior for this type of construction. A comparison of panel buckling load predictions using the present theory with the experimental data is also furnished.

Figure 1. Isogrid Plate Geometric Configuration

Figure 2. Notation and Sign Convention for an Equivalent Plate Element

FOUNDATIONS OF A NEW THEORY

Fundamental Assumptions

A typical isogrid plate with a quasi-isotropic skin appears in Figure 1. Notation and sign convention used in the theoretical development are shown in Figure 2. Four fundamental assumptions provide the basis for the new theory. The first is that transverse normal strain is neglected. The transverse displacement, w , is a function of x and y only as a consequence. The second is that transverse

shear strains in the ribs can be estimated from the statically equivalent shear stresses of classical theory. The third is that the Kirchhoff assumptions can be applied to the skin; this is equivalent to an assumption of skin thinness. The fourth is that the skin is isotropic with a Poisson's ratio of 1/3; this simplifies the equations considerably (10) as the triangular grid naturally possesses this effective Poisson's ratio.

Basic Equations

The shear strains are estimated from statically equivalent stresses of classical theory. These strain estimates permit the form of a suitable displacement field to be determined, which further leads to improved stresses. Displacement continuity is enforced at the rib-skin interface. These stresses are used to determine force and moment resultants. This procedure is described in detail in Reference 9. A summary of the basic equations is given in the Appendix.

APPLICATIONS

A quantitative demonstration for the theory is provided by the solution to the problem of panel buckling under uniaxial compression. Beam-like bending is studied first. This simple context permits a result to be obtained easily. The buckling stress resultant N_o is given by the following equation

$$\frac{N_{CL}}{N_o} = 1 + \pi^2 \frac{t^2}{a^2} k \quad (1)$$

N_{CL} is the classical stress resultant, t is the skin thickness and a is the panel length. The dimensionless parameter k defined by

$$k = 4 \left(\bar{\psi}_4 - \frac{B}{A} \bar{\psi}_2 \right) \frac{H}{t^2} \quad (2)$$

is a direct measure of the nonclassical effects provided by the theory. The quantities $\bar{\psi}_2$, $\bar{\psi}_4$, B , A and H are defined in the Appendix.

The form of equation (1) suggests the definition of a slenderness parameter

$$s = \frac{a}{t\sqrt{k}} \quad (3)$$

A value of approximately 5.0 for s is in the practical range. The predicted values of N_o from equation (1) are compared with the experimental values from Reference 6 in Table 1. The correlation is considered good in view of the scatter in the experimental data.

The case of an all simply supported square panel of side length a under uniaxial compressive loading N_o has been solved. The result can be cast in a form similar to equation (1). Additional insight is obtained by considering three representative stiffening configurations which are denoted light, medium and heavy. The values provided in Table 2 are based upon a modulus ratio E_I/G_I of 30; this is representative of modern graphite/epoxy material systems. E_I and G_I are the Young's modulus and shear modulus of the ribs, respectively. The ratio N_{CL}/N_o shows the relative importance of nonclassical effects.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A theory for bending-related behavior of isogrid stiffened plates has been presented and applied. The theory consistently accounts for the nonclassical influences that are important for isogrid configurations - - - transverse shear strain and nonclassical axial stresses in the ribs. Correlation of predictions with experimental results is good. These effects are significant in parameter ranges of practical interest and, hence, must be included in design analysis predictions.

Table 1. Comparison between Theoretical and Experimental Panel Buckling Loading Results.

Panel	Classical Theory	Critical Loading, lb/in.	
		Present Theory	Experiment
1-1	2677	2401	2706
1-2	2527	2260	2082
1-3	2513	2243	2235
1-4	2414	2161	1973
2-1	2269	2021	1937
2-2	2082	1851	1580
2-3	2231	1977	2268
2-4	2040	1825	1847
3-1	1909	1704	1524
3-2	1780	1594	1552

Table 2. Effect of Stiffening on the Nonclassical Contributions

Configuration	$\frac{bd}{ht} \left(\frac{E^1}{E^0} \right)^*$	d/t	Planar Bending Square Plate			
			k	N_{CL}/N_0	k	N_{CL}/N_0
Light Stiffening	0.5	4.0	136.78	1.034	227.27	1.056
Medium Stiffening	1.0	8.0	459.67	1.113	758.13	1.187
Heavy Stiffening	2.0	16.0	1450.75	1.358	2349.22	1.580

* E^1 and E^0 are the Young's moduli for rib and skin, respectively.

REFERENCES

1. Culp, J., "Stylus Weaving of Composite Structures", poster display at the 22nd AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials Conference, Atlanta, Georgia, April 1981.
2. Rehfield, L.W., Deo, R.B., "Buckling of Continuous Filament Advanced Composite Isogrid Wide Columns in Axial Compression", AFOSR-TR-79-0021, 1978.

3. Rehfield, L.W., Deo, R.B. and Renieri, G.D., "Continuous Filament Advanced Composite Isogrid: A Promising Structural Concept", Fibrous Composites in Structural Design, Plenum Publishing Corp., 1980, pp. 215-239.
4. Reddy, A.D., Rehfield, L.W., "Behavior of Continuous Filament Composite Isogrid Structure in Bending and Compression", AFOSR Report (Number to be assigned.), January 1981.
5. Rehfield, L.W., and Reddy, A.D., "Design Information for Continuous Filament Advanced Composite Isogrid Structures," Proceedings of the Fifth DOD/NASA Conference on Fibrous Composite in Structural Design, Held in New Orleans, LA, Volume 2, January 1981, pp. 113-143.
6. Rehfield, L.W., and Reddy, A.D., "Damage Tolerance Studies on Continuous Filament Graphite/Epoxy Isogrid Structures," Japan-US Conference Tokyo/Japan Proceedings on Composite Materials; Mechanics, Mechanical Properties and Fabrication, 1981, pp. 471-477.
7. Rehfield, L.W., and Murthy, P.L.N., "Toward a New Engineering Theory of Bending: Fundamentals," AIAA Journal, Vol. 20, No. 5, May 1982.
8. Rehfield, L.W. and Valisetty, R.R., "A Comprehensive Theory for Plates: Statics", submitted to AIAA Journal, 1982.
9. Yehezkely, O., and Rehfield, L.W., "A New Comprehensive Theory for Bending and Buckling of Stiffened Plates", presented at the 24th Israel Annual Conference on Aviation and Astronautics, Haifa, Israel, February 1982. To be published in the Israel Journal of Technology.
10. Isogrid Design Handbook, McDonnell Douglas Astronautics Company, Report MDC G4295A, February 1973.

APPENDIX

The basic equations encompass the following main categories:

Overall Equilibrium

$$N_{\beta\alpha,\beta} = 0 \quad (A-1)$$

$$M_{\beta\alpha,\beta} - Q_{\alpha} = 0 \quad (A-2)$$

$$Q_{\beta,\beta} + q = 0 \quad (A-3)$$

α and β assume the value of 1 and 2; 1 and 2 denote x and y. Repeated indices imply a sum of terms over the range of the index. N, M and Q are force, moment and transverse shear stress resultants, respectively. q is the lateral pressure acting on the skin in the z-direction.

Constitutive Relations

$$\frac{S}{6 \times 1} = \frac{K}{6 \times 6} \frac{\gamma}{6 \times 1} + \frac{S^*}{6 \times 1} \quad (A-4)$$

where \underline{S} is the generalized force resultant vector, $\underline{\gamma}$ the generalized strain vector, \underline{K} the stiffness matrix and \underline{S}^* is the desired refinement in the force resultant vector. They are

$$\underline{S}^T = [N_{xx}, N_{yy}, M_{xx}, M_{yy}, N_{xy}, M_{xy}] \quad (A-5)$$

$$\underline{Y}^T = [\epsilon_{xx}^0, \epsilon_{yy}^0, w_{,xx}, w_{,yy}, \gamma_{xy}^0, 2w_{,xy}] \quad (A-6)$$

usual notations for strain and curvature are used in equation (A-6). Superscript "0" denotes the skin.

$$\underline{K} = \begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{A}{3} & B & \frac{B}{3} & 0 & 0 \\ & A & \frac{B}{3} & B & 0 & 0 \\ & & D & \frac{D}{3} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & D & 0 & 0 \\ & \text{SYM.} & & & \frac{A}{3} & \frac{B}{3} \\ & & & & & \frac{D}{3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (A-7)$$

A, B and D are the axial, coupling and bending stiffnesses respectively.

$$A = \frac{9}{8} E^0 t (1 + \alpha) \quad (A-8)$$

$$B = \frac{9}{16} E^0 t^2 \alpha (1 + \delta) \quad (A-9)$$

$$D = \frac{3}{32} E^0 t^3 \left[1 + 4\alpha (\delta^2 + \frac{3}{2}\delta + \frac{3}{4}) \right] \quad (A-10)$$

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{b}{h} \frac{E^1}{E^0} \delta \quad (A-11)$$

$$\delta = d/t \quad (A-12)$$

E^1 and E^0 are the Young's moduli for rib and skin, respectively. b, d and h are dimensions of the isogrid shown in Figure 2.

$$S_{\alpha}^* = H \left\{ \bar{\psi}_{\alpha} (3N_{xx} - N_{yy})_{,xx} + \bar{\psi}_{\alpha+1} [(3M_{xx} - M_{yy})_{,xx} - q] \right\} \quad (A-13a)$$

$$S_{\alpha+1}^* = H \left\{ \bar{\psi}_{\alpha} (N_{yy} - 3N_{xx})_{,xx} + \bar{\psi}_{\alpha+1} [(M_{yy} - 3M_{xx})_{,xx} - 3q] \right\} \quad (A-13b)$$

$$S_{(\alpha+9)/2}^* = \left\{ H \bar{\psi}_{\alpha} (N_{yy} - 3N_{xx})_{,xy} + \bar{\psi}_{\alpha+1} [(M_{xy,xx} + 3M_{xy,yy} + 2M_{yy,xy})] \right\} \quad (A-13c)$$

α assumes the values 1 and 3, respectively, in the above, which provides six independent equations.

$$H = \frac{9 (E^1)^2}{32 h (AD - B^2)G^1} \quad (A-14)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_\alpha = D \bar{\phi}_\alpha - B \bar{\phi}_{\alpha+1} \quad (A-15)$$

$$\bar{\psi}_{\alpha+1} = -B \bar{\phi}_\alpha + A \bar{\phi}_{\alpha+1} \quad (A-16)$$

$$\bar{\phi}_1 = \delta t^3 \left[\frac{1}{2} (\delta + 1) (\delta + \frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{6} (\delta^2 + \frac{3}{2} \delta + \frac{3}{4}) \frac{1}{2} (\delta + \frac{1}{4}) \right] \quad (A-17)$$

$$\bar{\phi}_2 = \delta t^4 \left[\frac{1}{4} (\delta + 1) (\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 - \frac{1}{24} (\delta + 1) (\delta^2 + \delta + \frac{1}{2}) + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{12} - (\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 \right) \right] \quad (A-18)$$

$$\bar{\phi}_3 = \delta t^4 \left[\frac{1}{3} (\delta + \frac{1}{2}) (\delta^2 + \frac{3}{2} \delta + \frac{3}{4}) - \frac{1}{8} (1 + \delta) (\delta^2 + \delta + \frac{1}{2}) - \frac{1}{4} (\delta + \frac{1}{4}) (\delta + 1) \right] \quad (A-19)$$

$$\bar{\phi}_4 = \delta t^5 \left\{ \frac{1}{6} (\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 (\delta^2 + \frac{3}{2} \delta + \frac{3}{4}) - \frac{1}{30} \left[\frac{5}{2} \delta (\delta^2 + \delta + \frac{1}{2}) + \delta^4 + \frac{5}{16} \right] + \frac{1}{8} \left[\frac{1}{12} - (\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 \right] (\delta + 1) \right\} \quad (A-20)$$

Stresses

The stresses in the ribs are

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{E^1 (C_{1j} + z C_{3j}) (s_j - \underline{s}_j^*) + \frac{4h}{3b} H [F_{1j} \phi_1(z) + T_{1j} \phi_2(z)]}{s_{j,xx}} \quad (A-21a)$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{\frac{1}{4} E^1 [C_{1j} + 3C_{2j} + \sqrt{3} C_{5j} + z(C_{3j} + 3C_{4j} + \sqrt{3} C_{6j})] (s_j - \underline{s}_j^*) + \frac{h}{3b} H [F_{2j} \phi_1(z) + T_{2j} \phi_2(z)] (s_{j,xx} + 3s_{j,yy} + 2\sqrt{3} s_{j,xy})}{s_{j,xx} + 3s_{j,yy} + 2\sqrt{3} s_{j,xy}} \quad (A-21b)$$

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{\frac{1}{4} E^1 [C_{1j} + 3C_{2j} - \sqrt{3} C_{5j} + z(C_{3j} + 3C_{4j} - \sqrt{3} C_{6j})] (s_j - \underline{s}_j^*) + \frac{h}{3b} H [F_{3j} \phi_1(z) + T_{3j} \phi_2(z)] (s_{j,xx} + 3s_{j,yy} - 2\sqrt{3} s_{j,xy})}{s_{j,xx} + 3s_{j,yy} - 2\sqrt{3} s_{j,xy}} \quad (A-21c)$$

j assumes the values of 1, 2 and 3 respectively. σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_3 are stresses in rib-axis directions 1, 2 and 3, respectively (Figure 2). And

$$\frac{C}{6 \times 6} = \frac{K^{-1}}{6 \times 6} \quad (A-22)$$

$$\frac{F}{3 \times 6} = \begin{bmatrix} 3D & -D & -3B & B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2D & 0 & -2B & 2\sqrt{3}D & -2\sqrt{3}B \\ 0 & 2D & 0 & -2B & -2\sqrt{3}D & 2\sqrt{3}B \end{bmatrix} \quad (A-23)$$

$$\frac{T}{3 \times 6} = \begin{bmatrix} -3B & B & 3A & -A & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -2B & 0 & 2A & -2\sqrt{3}B & 2\sqrt{3}A \\ 0 & -2B & 0 & 2A & 2\sqrt{3}B & -2\sqrt{3}A \end{bmatrix} \quad (A-24)$$

$$\phi_1(z) = t(\delta + \frac{1}{2})z - \frac{1}{2}z^2 - \frac{1}{2}t^2(\delta + \frac{1}{4}) \quad (A-25)$$

$$\phi_2(z) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ t^2(\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 z - \frac{z^3}{3} - \frac{t^2}{2} \left[(\delta + \frac{1}{2})^2 - \frac{1}{12} \right] \right\} \quad (A-26)$$

The underlined terms are the nonclassical contributions.

The stresses in the skin are

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{9}{8}E^0 [C_{1j} + \frac{1}{3}C_{2j} + z(C_{3j} + \frac{1}{3}C_{4j})] (s_j - \underline{s_j^*}) \quad (A-27a)$$

$$\sigma_{yy} = \frac{9}{8}E^0 [C_{2j} + \frac{1}{3}C_{1j} + z(C_{4j} + \frac{1}{3}C_{3j})] (s_j - \underline{s_j^*}) \quad (A-27b)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{3}{8}E^0 (C_{5j} + zC_{6j})(s_j - \underline{s_j^*}) \quad (A-27c)$$

Usual notations for stress are used in equations (A-27).

Displacements

For ribs:

$$u_1 = U_1^0 - z w_{,1} + \frac{4h}{3b} H \frac{[F_{1j} \phi_1(z) + T_{1j} \phi_2(z)] S_{j,1}}{\quad} \quad (A-28a)$$

$$u_2 = U_2^0 - z w_{,2} + \frac{4h}{3b} H \frac{[F_{2j} \phi_1(z) + T_{2j} \phi_2(z)] S_{j,2}}{\quad} \quad (A-28b)$$

$$u_3 = U_3^0 - z w_{,3} + \frac{4h}{3b} H [F_{3j} \phi_1(z) + T_{3j} \phi_2(z)] S_{j,3} \quad (\text{A-28c})$$

U_1^0 , U_2^0 and U_3^0 represent the stretching of the skin mid-surface in rib-axis directions 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

For skin:

$$\begin{aligned} u^0 &= U^0 - z w_{,x} \\ v^0 &= V^0 - z w_{,y} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A-29})$$

U^0 and V^0 represent the stretching of the skin mid-surface in x and y-directions respectively.

10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 77, 78, 79, 80, 81, 82, 83, 84, 85, 86, 87, 88, 89, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 99, 100

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